

A Study on Consumer Attitude towards Eco-Friendly Products in Coimbatore City

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Abstract: "Green" is the expression of the day and "Green Marketing" and "Green Products" are eventual fate of the present makers and advertisers. Quickly changing climate is currently a main issue for individuals all through world, making them increasingly more worried about the climate. To have a supportable, contamination free climate, it is fundamental to execute the idea of green advertising, so that individuals are instructed in such manner however much as could reasonably be expected. In this way, it tends to be legitimately asserted that today individuals are starting to understand their job and obligations towards the climate. Albeit this change isn't going on rapidly, it is occurring. Organizations are looking towards acquiring an edge in the green market industry by attempting to repackage their items into a more natural amicable item. They are eliminating additional items and squandered materials and transforming their tasks into more proficient and green activity. Organizations are likewise beginning to instruct the majority with an increment in publicizing that puts accentuation on green items and how they are more gainful for the shoppers

Keywords: Green product, Green consumer, Corporate Social responsibility, Green marketing.

Introduction

“Green” is the word of the day and “Green Marketing” and “Green Products” are future of today’s manufacturers and marketers. Rapidly changing environment is now a major concern for the people throughout world, making them more and more concerned about the environment. To have a sustainable, pollution free environment, it is paramount to implement the concept of green marketing, so that people are educated in this regard as much as possible. Thus, it can be rightfully claimed that today people are beginning to realize their role and responsibilities towards the environment. Although this change is not happening quickly, it is happening. Businesses are looking towards gaining an edge in the green market

industry by trying to repackage their products into a more environmental friendly product. They are cutting down on extras and wasted materials and turning their operations into more efficient and green operation. Companies are also starting to educate the masses with an increase in advertising that puts emphasis on green products and how they are more beneficial for the consumers.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Green showcasing should fulfill two destinations: worked on natural quality and consumer loyalty. As the interest for green items without a doubt exists, green Marketing gives a chance to the organizations to expand their piece of the pie by presenting eco-accommodating items.

In light of an audit of the writing regarding the matter, Yasmin(2014) has recognized that industrialists and end-clients both are worried about eco-accommodating things. A higher level of them think that ecofriendly items are protected to burn-through. Time and on the notoriety of green items have caught large number of purchasers, along these lines expanding the interest for natural food things, garments, beauty care products, electronic and electrical things. Purchasers incline toward items with green ascribes. (Sehrawat,2014)

Rathod(2014) distinguishes the three specific sections of green buyers and investigates the difficulties and opportunities organizations have with green marketing. Jaya(2014) in this examination paper, principle accentuation has been made of idea, need and significance of green advertising. It explores the fundamental issues in reception of green advertising rehearses. The paper portrays the current Scenario of Indian market and investigates the difficulties have with green advertising.

Rakesh's (2013) principle accentuation has been made of idea, need and significance of green showcasing. The Paper targets discovering what's truly going on with really Green Marketing and how could a business firm be more serious by utilizing green promoting methodologies to acquire an upper hand over others. It investigates the fundamental issues in reception of green advertising rehearses.

Manjunath(2013) intends to concentrate on execution of Green Marketing drives in the Indian associations. The paper likewise intends to comprehend the ideas of Green Products; green advertising blend and calls attention to the difficulties before green promoting initiators.

Green promoting should fulfill two goals: worked on natural quality and consumer loyalty. As the demand for green items without a doubt exists, Green Marketing gives a chance to the organizations to increase their portion of the overall industry by presenting eco-friendly products. Based on a survey of the writing regarding the matter,

Yasmin(2014) has recognized that industrialists and end-clients both are concerned about eco-accommodating things. A higher rate of them think that eco friendly items are protected to consume. Time and on the ubiquity of green items have caught a large number of purchasers, along these lines expanding the interest for organic food things, garments, beauty care products, electronic and electrical things. Customers incline toward items with green attributes. (Sehrawat,2014)

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fundamental issues in reception of green marketing practices. The paper depicts the current Scenario of Indian market and investigates the difficulties have with green marketing.

Rakesh'S (2013) fundamental accentuation has been made of concept, need and significance of green advertising. The Paper points at finding out what really Green Marketing is about and how can a business firm be more cutthroat by utilizing green marketing systems to acquire an upper hand over others. It explores the principle issues in reception of green showcasing rehearses.

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NEED AND SIGNIFINACE OF GREENMARKETING

The subject of green marketing is vast, having important implications for business strategy and public policy. Clearly, green marketing is part and parcel of the overall corporate strategy (Menon and Menon, 1997). Green marketing also ties closely with issues of industrial ecology and environmental sustainability such as extended producers liability, life-cycle analysis, material use and resource flows, and eco-efficiency. In the present state of affairs, the prime focus now-a-days is to keep the customers as well as consumers in fold and even keep our natural environment safe Which is the biggest need of the time. Worldwide evidence indicates people are concerned about the environment and arechanging their behavior. Companies may lose many trustworthy and profitable clients due to absence of greenmanagement. In today's pioneering industry ofhigh technology due to growing community and consumer interests in green and socially responsible products, increased community pressure on companies to internalize externalities, such as health issues, neighborhood amenity, climate change; environmental and governmental legalizations and initiatives; innovative technologies and approaches of dealing with pollution, improved resource and energy efficiency, and to retain old (loyal and profitable) customers and consumers, it is very much urgent to implement green marketing. As a consequence, green management provides new environment friendly customers which lead to increase in sales and profits of an organization that further leads to expansion and growth of business. This enhances the public image of the company. There are many misconceptions about Green Productsthat hurt the hopes for green products like that —such products are of lower quality or don't really deliver ontheir environmental promisesll (Bloom, 2004, p. 79).

It isknown all over the world that people are concerned about the environment and are changing their behavior.Various regulatory bodies and acts are set to ensure environmental safety and protection, some of which include, OSHA (Occupational Safety and health Act),CERCLA (Comprehensive environmental Respond Compensation liability Act), TSCA (Toxic Substance Control Act), HMTA (the Hazardous Material Transportation Act), FIFRA (Federal Insecticide, Fungicide and Rodenticide Act), FFDC (Federal food, Drug and Cosmetic Act, Clean Air Act, Clean Water Act,GHS (Globally Harmonized System of Classification and labeling of Chemicals).Worldwide evidence indicates people are concernedabout the environment and are changing their behavior. The studies show the links between air pollutants andlow birth weight, premature birth, still birth and infant death. As resources are limited and human wants are unlimited, it is important for the marketers to fully utilize the resources to achieve the organizationalobjectives.There is increasing interest among the consumers across the globe on the subject of

protection of environment. Hence, green marketing is unavoidable. As a result of this, green marketing has emerged which speaks for growing market for sustainable and socially responsible products and service

Objectives

- To study the consumer attitude for Eco-friendly products.
- To identify the factor that influences consumer to purchase green product.
- To know the opinion about the price of Eco-friendly product.
- To identify the attractive media of advertisement of Eco-friendly products.

Sample Size

Thus 120 respondents were chosen for this survey.

Research Design and Methodology

The research design is useful for conducting the research work. The research design adopted for this study is empirical. Primary data is the chief source for the research work. In this study, questionnaire method has been used to collect the primary data. Secondary data collected from journals, books, other projects and websites. The sampling design of the study was conducted by convenient sampling method.

Table 1: Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Educational Qualification	Respondents	Percentage
School Level	21	17
UG Degree	45	38
PG Degree	33	27
Others	21	18
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

It is inferred from the above table that, out of 120 respondents, 17% of them comes under the qualification of school level. 38% of the respondents falls under the qualification of UG Degree. 27% of the respondents comes under the qualification of PG Degree and 18% of the respondents are Others.

Table 2: The Family Members of the Respondents

Family Members	Respondents	Percentage
1 to 2 members	8	7
3 to 4 members	64	53
4 to 6 members	32	27
Above 6 members	16	13
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

It is inferred from the above table that, out of 120 respondents, 7% of them are having 1 to 2 members in a family. 53% of the respondent's family include 3 to 4 members. 27% of the respondent's family include 4 to 6 members and 13% of the respondents of family include Above 6 members.

Table 3: Reason for Selecting the Particular Brand by the Respondents

Level of awareness	Respondents	Percentage
Very High	14	12
High	24	20
Moderate	50	41
Low	32	27
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

It is inferred from the above table that, out of 120 respondents, 12% of the respondents awareness is very high. 20% of the respondent's awareness are high. 50% of the respondents Awareness is Moderate of and 27% of the respondent's awareness are too low.

Table 4: Influencing Media by the Respondents

Media of awareness	Respondents	Percentage
Television	72	60
Radio	18	15
Newspaper	24	20
Trade Fair/Exhibitions	6	5
Total	120	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

It is inferred from the above table that, out of 120 respondents, 70% of the people are influenced by the media of Television. 11% of the respondents are influenced by the media of Radio. 13% of the respondents are influenced by the media of Newspaper and 6% of the respondents are influenced by the media of Trade fair and exhibitions.

Correlation: Cross Table between the Occupations with Opinion about Reason for Purchasing Eco-Friendly Products

<i>X</i>	<i>Y</i>	<i>X</i>	<i>Y</i>	<i>XY</i>	<i>X²</i>	<i>y²</i>
72	29	42	-1	-42	1764	1
18	50	-12	20	-240	144	400
24	32	-6	2	-12	36	4
6	9	-24	-21	504	576	441
120	120	0	0	210	2520	846

$$r = \frac{\sum XY}{\sqrt{\sum X^2 \sum y^2}}$$
$$r = \frac{210}{\sqrt{2520 \times 846}}$$
$$r = \frac{210}{\sqrt{2131920}}$$
$$r = \frac{210}{1460.10}$$

$$r = 0.143$$

Interpretation

From the above table, it could be clearly observed that the 0.143% of the respondents between the occupation and opinion on about the reason for purchasing eco-friendly products.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This review was led to comprehend the buyer mentality towards green advertising and to distinguish the variables identified with the conviction and inspiration to buy green item by the purchaser in Coimbatore City. Greater part of individuals don't know about green item and their employments. Shopper's steadfastness is the main component used to take choice for buying green item by the buyer. However it isn't obvious to the overall individuals what sort of advantage are including in natural agreeable items yet the review uncover that because of a dangerous atmospheric deviation shopper are intrigued to buy green item. Different elements are nature of item, additional value, use as extravagance or flaunting nature and ecological mindfulness and so on We can inspire our buyers towards green advertising by various mindfulness program. For green promoting to be powerful we need to keep three things; be certifiable, instruct our clients and offer them chance to rehearse. Advertisers need to comprehend the ramifications of green promoting. Assuming we think clients are not worried about ecological issues or won't pay a premium for items that are more eco capable, reconsider. We should track down a chance to improve item's presentation and fortify our client's devotion. Green advertising is as yet in its outset and there is an adequate degree to direct concentrate further on one more gathering of individuals to recognize additional impacting factors in such manner.

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